

HISTORY

THE RELATIONS OF THE TURKS WITH THE EASTERN SLAVS, ETHNOPOLITICAL PROCESSES

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Abstract

In the mid-10th century, a significant Oghuz community was visible in the lands north of the Black Sea. Russian historians recorded them as Tork, and Byzantine sources as Uz. For the first time in Russian chronicles, Torks and Kipchaks are mentioned, whom they called Polovtsy (fair-haired). It is not known why the Russians, excluding the Pechenegs and Kipchaks, called Uz only Torkom. The Kipchak raids led to the arrival of the Torks in the north of the Black Sea. The Kipchaks continued to put pressure on the Oguzes in the north of the Black Sea region, as a result of which a significant part of them descended to the Danube, and from there to the Balkans. The Oguzes, who crossed the Danube in 1064-1065, split into many branches and carried out a large-scale invasion of the Balkans, plundering the regions of Thrace, Macedonia and Thessaloniki. However, a sudden cold caused an epidemic among them. This epidemic weakened the Oghuz people, who were essentially scattered and attacked by their former Pecheneg relatives and local residents, resulting in many casualties and loss of power and importance. Over time, the Torcs, who had forgotten their old traditions, language and religion and assimilated among the Russians and other Slavic peoples, became one of the elements that shaped the ethnogenesis of these peoples.

Keywords: Torquay, Kievan Rus, Oguzes, Kipchaks, Gokturks Khazars.

Introduction. Nomadic Turkic tribes, who left a significant mark in history, for various reasons were forced to leave their homeland, the ancient Turkestan region, and migrate to the west. During these migration movements, they fought sometimes with their relatives, and sometimes with other tribes to establish their dominance in the regions where they came. One of these tribes of Turkic origin were the Uzs, who left their homeland and spread to the west. At the beginning of the tenth century, they followed the Pechenegs to the northern regions of the Black Sea region and settled on new lands. When the Pechenegs and Torks came to the steppes around the Black and Caspian Seas, this region was under the rule of the Khazars, who managed to create a very powerful state [1. 56]. During the time of the Gokturk Empire, the Torks lived on the land of this majestic empire, as a tribe that was part of the Oguz tribe. Torks lived in large numbers in the vicinity of Issyk-Kul and Lake Balkhash. After the collapse of the Gokturk state, they became subjects of Turkesh. The Turkesh state was weakened and collapsed as a result of China's policy. After that, the Turks founded a new state in Inner Asia. In historical records, this state is referred to as the Karluk State. The Torks, who could not establish good relations with the Karluk state because of their loyalty to the Turkesh Khanate. As a result, the Torks rebelled against the Karluks. They were unable to resist the powerful Karluk state and chose to migrate to the west instead of submitting to the Karluks. This migration movement of the Torcs will begin a process that will tear them away from their homeland and erase them from the stage of history. The main reason for writing this article is about the Turks who left their lands in Central Asia in the early Middle Ages and undertook a difficult journey to Eastern Europe. Unfortu-

nately, there are very few scientific articles about torques. In this article we will try to shed light on the arrival of the Torks in Eastern Europe, the Pecheneg-Tork relations, as well as the fact that the Torks forced the Pechenegs to migrate to the west. We will also give place to Byzantine relations with the Torcs. Let's try to explain the relationship between the Torcs and the Russians and the settlement of the Torcs on the territory of the state of Kievan Rus. The article will discuss the formation of the ethnogenesis of the Eastern Slavs by mixing the Torcs with the Russians.

Actuality of the article.

When the Torks and other groups of Oghuz migrated to the West, fleeing from the policy of annexation of the Karluks, they were attacked by other States. These populous and warlike tribes posed a threat to every surrounding state. Because of their nomadic way of life, these tribes could not settle on a certain land. This wave of migration of the Oguz tribes for about 50 years dragged them into the deserts around the Caspian and Black Seas. At the end of the X century, the Torks lived independently within the Khazar khaganate and were not subjects of any state [1 .87]. The Black Sea region was politically more livable for the Turks than Inner Asia. The Torks, who continued to exist in this region, were not subjected to the annexation policy against them by the Khazars. However, the Caspian region was not suitable enough for nomadic animal husbandry and tribal life, unlike the Asian steppes. For this reason, they turned to plunder on the trade routes of the Khazar Khaganate. The attacks of the Torks on trade caravans began to create economic problems for the Khazar state. The Khazars did not seek to completely get rid of the Torcs, the most important reason for this was that they used Torcs against the Pechenegs. Since the Torks settled between the Khazar state and the

Pechenegs, they prevented the plundering of the Pechenegs of the inner parts of the Khazar Khaganate. It was very difficult to fight with a regular army against the Torcs, who could move quickly and did not own a certain land. For this reason, the Khazar Khaganate concluded an agreement with the Pechenegs, another Oghuz tribe, to fight against the Torcs. By forcing these two related tribes to fight against each other, the Khazars managed to weaken both sides. The pressure of the bonds (Torcs) on the Pechenegs was not temporary. The bonds, which first opposed the Pechenegs at the request of the Khazar state, then continued the struggle for strengthening, subjugating the Pechenegs, who, like themselves, were Turkic tribes. The Pechenegs, who were a very numerous tribe, were not defeated as a result of this pressure from the Oguz, but when they could not overcome the intense attacks of the Oguz (uz, tork), they began to migrate north of the Caspian Sea. to reach more distant lands. This migration of the Pechenegs did not end in the north of the Caspian Sea [2 .43] . They advanced to the Volka River, which was a fertile land for the Pechenegs with its swamps and rich nature. The Torks, who followed the Pechenegs, followed them to new lands. These lands were very fertile and rich in summer, but because of the harsh climate in winter they did not have the nature to which the Pechenegs and Torks were accustomed. For this reason, first the Pechenegs, then the Torques. The Pechenegs crossed the Itil River and moved west, into the depths of Europe. Northeastern Europe was not under the rule of the great powers at the time when the Pechenegs began their migration movement. For this reason, the Pechenegs, who had the opportunity to move widely, moved further west and reached the Hungarian lands. The Torcs continued their movement after the Pechenegs . The Hungarian state was one of the small states that the Byzantine Empire considered one of the barbarian tribes. At that time, the Byzantine Empire was fighting with barbarian tribes, using another barbarian tribe, with a Northern policy developed by it. When these tribes living in the north of the Black Sea posed a danger to Byzantium, Byzantium sent gifts to other tribes and established good relations[2.45], forcing them to fight against tribes that posed a danger to himself. The Hungarians, whose population was small, were able to continue their existence, obeying the northern policy of Byzantium. The Hungarians, the first tribe that the Pechenegs encountered when entering the Northern Black Sea region, were not strong enough to resist the Pechenegs. The Pechenegs also sought new lands for themselves and attacked Hungarian lands (893). The Hungarians, unable to resist the Pecheneg armies advancing from the east, had to migrate to the west. The Pechenegs settled in the new lands they had liberated from the Hungarians. Their main dwelling was the land between the Don and Denepir rivers. The Torks settled in the west of the Pechenegs and continued to organize predatory campaigns against them and other tribes along the Northern Black Sea coast. In the new lands there was no tribe capable of resisting the Pechenegs and Torks. With the arrival of the Pechenegs and Torcs, the Slavic tribes also changed places. Some Slavs migrated to the west, some to the north, and some

to the Balkans. During this period, the Pechenegs, Slavs and Torcs, who dominated the geography of the Northern Black Sea region (900), became border neighbors. Slavs and Pechenegs have been neighbors on these lands for more than two centuries. Sometimes they fought with each other, sometimes they cooperated and lived peacefully[3 . 75]. The atmosphere of peace and tranquility between the Turks and the Slavs persisted for ten centuries. These two Powers, without threatening each other, entered into trade and military cooperation within the framework of peaceful relations. In addition, the Torks, who believed in "Tengirism", got acquainted with Christianity when they began to establish good relations with the Slavs. The religious beliefs of the Pechenegs and Torcs began to be influenced by Western Slavs who had Orthodox beliefs. In this respect, the Pechenegs and Torks were the first Turkic tribes to adopt Christianity en masse. Then the Bonds also adopted the Orthodox faith. Slavs borrowed steppe military culture and advanced military strategies from the Pechenegs. The Slavic military organization, which stood out with slower and foot forces, gained a significant advantage by mastering the cavalry and highly mobile military maneuvers of the Torcs. These advantages made the Pechenegs and Torks the most powerful "barbarian" tribe in Europe. The Torcs lived a peaceful life in the Northern Black Sea region thanks to their relations with their Slavic neighbors, with whom they got along well. This peace of the Turks was disrupted by another Turkish migration that came from the Caspian Sea. This time, the Kumankipchaks were on the way of migration from the north of the Caspian Sea to the lands around the Northern Black Sea region. The union of the Polovtsians and Kipchaks attacked the lands of the Torks [8 . 89]. The Torcs also migrated to the West under the influence of the Polovtsian-Kipchak invasions. With this wave of migration, the Torcs who crossed the Denepir River came to the lands where the Pechenegs lived. The Torks were more numerous than the Pechenegs and outnumbered them militarily. Unable to resist the populous invasions of Tork, the Pechenegs in the period from 943 to 972 gradually began to lose their influence in the lands along the Don River and began to retreat to the Diyenper Creek. Torquay continued to establish good relations with the Western Slavs during this period[5 .156]. However, after the death of Igor, a relative of Kievan Rus, in 965, Svyatoslav took his place, which marked the beginning of a bad course in the relations of the Tork-Slavs. Svyatoslav, known as "Alexander the Great among Russians," pursued a militant and expansionist policy. Unlike other Slavic princes, Svyatoslav, who lived a modest life on horseback and at the head of his army, was a commander with superior military qualities, like the Pecheneg and Tork khans. As soon as Svyatoslav took over, he began preparing for war and went on his first campaign, attacking the Volga Bulgarians. Then he organized campaigns against the Danube Bulgarians, and then against the Khazar khaganate. Svyatoslav's campaign in the Khazar Khaganate became an opportunity for the Torks. The Torks, who attacked Kiev in the absence of Svyatoslav, failed and were repulsed. At the beginning of the IX century, Tsar Simeon became the head of the

Danube Bulgar state. Simeon occupied most of the Byzantine lands in the Balkans. In 914, he captured the city of Adrantipol. then he destroyed all of Thrace. The Byzantine government gave the necessary instructions to the Byzantine General Bogas, who lived in the city of Chersonesos (Crimea). General Bogasa contacted the Pechenegs and Torks, trying to force them to move against the Bulgarians. In 917, the Oguzes moved against the Danube Bulgarians. However, after General Bogas, who commanded the Byzantine army, and Admiral Lakapin quarreled with each other, the Oguzes could not trust the Byzantines and returned. During this period, the Byzantine government attached great importance to the Oguzes (Pechenegs and Torks) and understood that it was necessary to get along with the Oguzes. Friendly relations were established between Byzantium and the Oghuz. When the Byzantine Emperor Basil II decisively defeated the Bulgarians in 1018, the Pecheneg-Byzantine relations entered a new phase. They became neighbors on the Danube River. The Pechenegs and Torques will cross the Danube at the first opportunity and settle in the Balkans[6. 45]. Meanwhile, Torquay found themselves in a difficult situation as a result of the pressure of the Bonds coming from the north. Some Torcs even joined the Byzantine service with the Pechenegs and served the Byzantine Empire in Anatolia. Meanwhile, some of them sided with Alparslan in the Battle of Manzikert and played an effective role in the outcome of the war. In the 1050s, large expansionist movements of the Pechenegs and Torcs were observed in the Balkans, and between 1081 and 1091 this situation even intensified, facilitating the conquest of Anatolia by the Seljuks. In 1086, the Torques moved to Constantinople together with the Hungarian king under the leadership of the Pecheneg king Chelgu. Chelgu was wounded in the war and died. Under the leadership of his successor Tatush, they defeated the Byzantine army, reinforced by the Polovtsians, in Derster (Silistra) (1087). But it was the northern policy that saved Byzantium[7.154]. The Byzantine government concluded an agreement with the Cumans who came to the Balkans after the Bond. The Polovtsians inflicted a heavy defeat first to the Pechenegs, and then to the Torcs in the area of Omurbey (Lebinium) on the banks of Evros. Part of the Torcs went with the Pechenegs to Hungary and settled in the vicinity of Pest and Ferte. Some Turks mixed with Uzs and Polovtsians. Those who remained in the Balkans were settled in Vardar. It is said that the Vlach meglons in Macedonia and the shop Bulgars around Sofia are descendants of the Pechenegs and Torks. The name Tork is still alive in some toponyms and folk legends of Anatolia, Serbia, Russia, Hungary and the Caucasus.

After the arrival of the Torks in Eastern Europe, they accepted the power of the Khazar Empire and lived for some time under the rule of the Khazars. later, the Polovtsians who followed them pushed the Torok to the west. The Torcs invaded the lands of the Pechenegs and forced them to migrate to the west. Thus, these peoples,

who persecuted each other, were forced to migrate to the depths of Europe and to the lands of Byzantium. The settlers who settled on the new lands adopted the traditions of the local population and were eventually erased from the historical scene. The displacement of the Pechenegs by the Turks into the depths of Western Europe also affected the Hungarian tribes who settled in the west of the Pechenegs. Since the Hungarians could not resist the attacks of the Pechenegs, they began to move towards Central Europe. Many German and Slavic peoples, unable to withstand the attacks of the Hungarians, were forced to change. these events influenced the further development of the Western Slavs. Part of the Turks moved south and crossed the Byzantine borders. During the wars with its neighbors, the Byzantine army, which was experiencing difficulties due to a shortage of military personnel, strengthened its army at the expense of hired mounted units of Turks and Pechenegs. The strengthened Byzantine army began to achieve success in wars with its neighbors. The arrival of the Turks in Byzantium prolonged the life of the disintegrating Byzantine Empire for several centuries. The Turks settled in the Byzantine and Russian lands, some of them converted to Christianity and assimilated, while others retained their national identity as Gagauz.

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